

Ichthyofaunal Diversity of Ghaghara River in and Around Siwan District (Bihar), India

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Abstract

Bihar provides considerable potential for the development of inland fisheries and aquaculture, in addition to its abundant aquatic bioresource potential. In order to look into the ichthyofaunal variety of Siwan, Bihar, data were gathered over the course of a year in 2021–2022, with the assistance of knowledgeable local fish growers and fishermen from various parts of the district. Lakes, ponds, irrigation canals, and rivers (Ghaghara, Daha) were the sources of the collections. Sixty-two fish species from twenty families, forty genera, and eight orders were discovered throughout the research period. With 22 species (35.48%), the Order of Cypriniformes was the most dominant, followed by Siluriformes with 20 species (32.25%) and Perciformes with 9 species (14.51%). The current study demonstrated that while SIWAN has a high diversity of fish, appropriate conservation measures are needed to preserve the district's sustainability and species richness.

Keywords Fish diversity, Species Composition, Siwan, Bihar.

Introduction

Numerous factors contribute to the diversity of life on Earth, starting with genes and continuing to the abundance and intricacy of species, life forms, and functional functions. These elements are arranged spatially in biological communities, ecosystems, regions, and beyond (Colwell, 2009). Stated differently, it refers to the diversity and heterogeneity of living things, their genetic variations, and the environments in which they coexist. Rich biodiversity is a result of the varied climate and physical geography. Various viewpoints from people in different fields have led to varied opinions on biodiversity. It has also been referred to as "life" or the "wilderness" on several occasions.

Objective of study

The main objective of this research paper is to study the ichthyofaunal diversity in and around river Ghaghra in Siwan district (Bihar), India.

Review of Literature

The difficulty of finding uncommon species and the underlying complexity of the environmental template make it difficult to quantify patterns of variety at the species level, even when the creatures are known to science. According to Winter and Hughes (1997), biodiversity is the variance in the genetic makeup and life forms of populations, species, groups, and ecosystems. The ability of biological systems to adapt to environmental changes is influenced by biodiversity, which is also necessary for ecosystems to produce goods and services like clean water and nutrient cycling (Rahbek and Colwell, 2011). Bihar provides significant potential for the development of inland fisheries and aquaculture, as well as great potential for aquatic bioresources. About 8.32% of the nation's overall fish diversity comes from the State (Lakra, 2010). In addition to 98.3 lakh ha of flood plain lakes and abandoned water, there are 18,350 km of rivers and canals, 2.36 lakh ha of reservoirs, 61 lakh ha of ponds and tanks that are home to aquatic resources. The state produces 2.11 million tonnes of fish in total from all of its resources (2021–2022). During the last few decades, the fish biodiversity of the state are declining rapidly due to introduction of exotic fish species (Dwivedi and Nautiyal, 2010; Pathak *et al*, 2011) and anthropogenic environmental degradation like urbanization, damming, abstraction of water for irrigation and power generation and pollution, which have subjected natural water bodies in general and rivers, in particular to severe stress with devastating effects on freshwater fish diversity (Lakra, 2010). The current state of ichthyofaunal variety was to be examined, and the first comprehensive description of fishes in district Siwan (Bihar) was to be provided.

Methodology

Data Collection: The data were collected with the help of local skilled fishermen from different locations, fish farmers and fish markets from different locations of SIWAN (Fig. 1) for 12 months during 2021-22. The latitude of Siwan, Bihar, India is **26.219621**, and the longitude is **84.356658**. **Siwan, Bihar, India** is located at *India* country in the *Cities* place category with the gps coordinates of 26° 13' 10.6392" N and 84° 21' 23.9724" E.

Sources : Rive Map Siwan, 2022

Table 1 : Fish diversity of SIWAN District (BIHAR).

Order	Family	Scientific name	Local/common name
Osteoglossiformes	Notopteridae	<i>Chitala chitala</i>	Moi/ knifefish
		<i>Notopterus notopterus</i>	Patra/ featherback
Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	<i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i>	Dhawai
		<i>Aristichthys nobilis</i>	Bighead carp
		<i>Aspidoparia morar</i>	Moraki
		<i>Catla catla</i>	Bhukur/ Catla
		<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i>	Nain/ Mrigal
		<i>Cirrhina reba</i>	Raia
		<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i>	Grass carp
		<i>Cyprinus carpio communis</i>	Common carp
		<i>Cyprinus carpio specularis</i>	Common carp
		<i>Cyprinus carpio nudus</i>	Common carp
		<i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i>	Silver carp
		<i>Labeo angra</i>	Rain
		<i>Labeo bata</i>	Bata
		<i>Labeo calbasu</i>	Karonchh
		<i>Labeo dero</i>	Kalabans
		<i>Labeo gonius</i>	Kurai
		<i>Labeo rohita</i>	Rohu
		<i>Osteobrama cotio</i>	Gurda
<i>Puntius chola</i>	Sidhari		
<i>Puntius sarana</i>	Barb/ Olive barb		
<i>Puntius sophore</i>	Pool barb		
<i>Puntius ticto</i>	Ticto barb		

Siluriformes	Bagridae	<i>Sperata aor</i>	Whiskered catfish
		<i>Sperata seenghala</i>	Giant river-catfish
		<i>Mystus bleekeri</i>	Day's mystus
		<i>Mystus cavasius</i>	Gangetic mystus
		<i>Mystus menoda</i>	Menoda catfish
		<i>Mystus tengra</i>	Tengara
		<i>Mystus vittatus</i>	Striped dwarf catfish
		<i>Rita rita</i>	Belgagra/Rita
	Siluridae	<i>Ompak bimaculatus</i>	Pabda/butter catfish
		<i>Wallago attu</i>	Pahin/ Wallago
	Schilbeidae	<i>Ailia coilia</i>	Patasi/ Gangetic ailia
		<i>Clupisoma garua</i>	Garua
		<i>Eutropiichthys vacha</i>	Vacha
		<i>Silonia silondia</i>	Siland
Sisoridae	<i>Bagarius bagarius</i>	Goonch	
	<i>Gagata cenia</i>	Gagata	
	Clariidae	<i>Clarias batrachus</i>	Mangur
		<i>Clarias gariepinus</i>	Bidesi magur
	Heteropneustidae	<i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i>	Singhi
	Pangasiidae	<i>Pangasius pangasius</i>	Pangas catfish
Perciformes	Channidae	<i>Channa marulius</i>	Sauri
		<i>Channa punctatus</i>	Sauri
		<i>Channa striatus</i>	Sauri
	Anabantidae	<i>Anabas testudineus</i>	Kawai
	Ambassidae	<i>Chanda baculis</i>	Chanri
		<i>Chanda nama</i>	Chanri
		<i>Parambassis ranga</i>	Chanri
	Cichlidae	<i>Oreochromis mossambicus</i>	Tilapia
Nandide	<i>Nandus nandus</i>	Dhebari	
Clupeiformes	Clupeidae	<i>Gudusia chapra</i>	Suhia
		<i>Tenualosa ilisha</i>	Hilsa/ Hilsa shad
Beloniformes	Belonidae	<i>Xenentodon cancila</i>	Kauwa
Synbranchiformes	Mastacembelidae	<i>Mastacembelus armatus</i>	Bam/ Zig-zag eel
		<i>Mastacembelus pancalus</i>	Malga/barred spiny eel
	Synbranchidae	<i>Amphipnous cuchia</i>	Andhasanp/Cuchia
Mugiliformes	Mugilidae	<i>Rhinomugil corsula</i>	Corsula
		<i>Sicamugil cascasia</i>	Yellowtail mullet
Tetraodontiformes	Tetraodontidae	<i>Tetraodon cutcutia</i>	Ocellated Pufferfish

Plate-1. Some Important fishes of Ghaghara River (Siwan)

Samples were taken from fish markets, lakes, tanks, rivers (Daha and Ghaghara), and irrigation canals. The primary river, Ghaghara, runs the whole length of the district from west to east. One of the most significant rivers for catch fishing is this one. After being transported to the lab for additional research, the captured fish were first treated with 8% formalin for 48 hours, and then they were stored in 5% formalin.

Identification of Fishes: Fish identities were determined using either preserved or fresh specimens. The FAO Identification Sheets, Srivastava (2002), Day (1878), Talwar and Jhingran (1991), and ITIS (Integrated Taxonomic Information System) Standard Report were the standard taxonomic keys used to identify them. Fish were gathered, and species-level identification was done.

Result and Discussion

The only freshwater fishing resources found in Siwan were capture fisheries from rivers, nullas, and irrigation canals, as well as culture fisheries from seasonal, permanent and cultural ponds. The majority of the fish species that are currently found in the river are either naturally reproducing or have escaped from the several bodies of water in the area. 62 fish species from 20 Families, 9 Orders, and 41 Genera were discovered during the current research (Table 1). The Order Cypriniformes (22 species) provided the most to the analysis, followed by the Siluriformes (20 species) and the Perciformes (9 species). Beloniformes and Tetraodontiformes shared just one species, whereas Clupeiformes, Mugiliformes, and Osteoglossiformes contributed two species each, and Synbranchiformes shared three (Fig. 2). The Family Cyprinidae included *Amblypharyngodon mola*, *Aristichthys nobilis*, *Aspidoparia morar*, *Catla catla*, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, *C. reba*, *Ctenopharyngodon idella*, *Labeo angra*, *L. bata*, *L. calbasu*, *L. dero*, *L. gonius*, *L. rohita*, *Osteobrama cotio*, *Puntius chola*, *Puntius sarana*, *Puntius sophore*, and *Puntius ticto* were the most abundant order (35.48%) (Fig. 3). The leading genus was *Labeo*, which had six species, followed by *Puntius*, which had four species. 20 species (32.25%) were provided by the Order Siluriformes. The Bagridae family of the Siluriformes accounted

for 12.9% of all fish species, with the Schilbeidae coming in second at 6.45%, Sisoridae at 3.22%, Clariidae at 3.22%, Siluridae at 3.22%, Heteropneustidae at 1.61%, and Pangasiidae at 1.61%. The Perciformes family provided nine species, or 14.51%. According to Figure 4, the major families of Perciformes were Channidae (4.83%) and Ambassidae (4.83%), followed by Anabantidae (1.61%), Cichlidae (1.61%), and Nandidae (1.61%).

Species that were prevalent in the district and found in the culture ponds were *Catla catla*, *Labeo rohita*, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, *Ctenopharyngodon idella*, *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*, and *Cyprinus carpio*. In the ponds and rivers, tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*) and *C. carpio* were observed. The common fish species in the seasonal ponds were *Wallago attu*, *Clarias batrachus*, *Puntius spp.*, and *Heteropneustes fossilis*. Significant carp and catfish populations in India were also often reported in the rivers and irrigation canals.

The district of Siwan has 62 species of fish, indicating a high degree of fish variety. The riverine system's fisheries rely on a sizable number of species and a variety of fishing gear. The district's declining fish biodiversity is mostly due to habitat degradation, foreign fish invasions, and fishing pressure (Lakra et al, 2008; Lakra, 2010). The fish variety found in this research is lower than that found in previous reports (Pandey, 1999; Dwivedi et al, 2004)—it is 17 species lower in Pandey's 1999 report and 15 species lower in Dwivedi et al's 2007 report. This discrepancy may be due to the huge geographic regions covered in the prior studies. The richness and composition of fish communities are influenced by fishing pressure and environmental stress (Dwivedi and Nautiyal, 2010; Mayank et al, 2011; Kumar, 2012; Tamboli and Jha, 2012). The current study shows that the fish variety in the Siwan area (Bihar) is shifting.

Thirty species are documented in sections of the Ganga River at Allahabad, while reports of the existence of 87 fish species from the eastern portion of Bihar and 111 taxa from Bihar and Bihar exist (Srivastava, 2002; Lakra, 2010). According to Lakra (2010), the river Betwa, which is a tributary of the Ganga basin recognized under the First River - Linking Plan of India, is home to 63 fish species, 20 Families, and 45 Genera. More recently, the NBFGR in BIHAR documented 92 fish species from the Ganga River, representing 58 Genera and 24 Families. 56 species from 20 Families, 42 Genera, and 7 Orders were found in the Gomti River, according to another research (Sarkar et al, 2010). Bihar is home to around 123 different fish species, according to a recent evaluation conducted by NBFGR, Lucknow (Lakra, 2010).

Out of 123 species, around 33% are regarded as decorative, roughly 57% are possible food, and 10% are identified as prospective sport fish when Bihar's use pattern is evaluated (Lakra, 2010). Environmental hazards may arise from both natural and man-made sources, or from a mix of interconnected and cascading effects. Preservation and wise use of natural resources.

Fig. 2 : Order-wise distribution of fish species.

Fig. 3 : Diagrammatic representation of % contribution in each Order.

Fig. 4 : Diagrammatic representation of the number of species occurring in each Family

Fig. 5 : Diagrammatic representation of the % contribution in each Family.

Following the signing of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD, 1992), resources became a worldwide problem. Fish taxa in BIHAR's freshwater resources are alarmingly declining at the moment as a result of several human activities. The overall pool diversity has been linked to a number of factors, including destructive fishing methods (Dwivedi and Nautiyal, 2010), the introduction of exotic species (Singh and Mishra, 2001; Lakra et al, 2008; Pathak et al, 2011), habitat alteration and water diversion (Jagera et al, 2001), low vegetation cover in the catchment areas, siltation, water abstraction, and low water velocity

(Mayank et al, 2011); and. Though not much published literature is available on the threat status of fish species of BIHAR, yet it is fact that population of some species is constantly going down and there is an urgent need to protect the same for posterity. According to recent conservation assessment of NBFGR, a total of 20 freshwater fishes are categorized as threatened of which 9 under Endangered and 11 Vulnerable (Lakra, 2010). The Government of Bihar has declared endangered *Chitala chitala* as a State Fish and planning for its conservation is in process (NBFGR, www.nbfgres.in). Due to lack of previous sufficient information on occurrence and abundance of fish species of Siwan, it is not possible to quantify the rate of decline in its diversity but this report would be useful as baseline data for any future assessment and conservation plan for fisheries. However, more awareness and motivation is required on the value of indigenous fish diversity and conservation of aquatic resources to ensure the sharing of benefits of its utilization in an equitable manner so that the aquatic ecosystem gets adequate time to recover its natural community structure (Lakra and Pandey, 2009; Lakra, 2010).

Conclusion

The abundant diversity of freshwater fish documented by this investigation can be used to inform ichthyofaunal diversity and management decisions in a scientific practice. Additionally, additional conservation initiatives are urgently needed in the Bihar region in order to preserve this unique freshwater heritage.

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